

The use of stone waste as fine aggregate or cement replacement in cement-based mortars: A review

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ABSTRACT

Mortar is the second most used construction material. Its limitations are apparent with the growing demand for environmental protection. Reducing the use of cement and fine aggregate is a priority. Concurrently, quarrying activities, mineral-asphalt mixes, and dimension stone industry generate fine waste, presenting significant environmental challenges. However, due to its fineness, this waste can fulfil the requirements of fine aggregate or filler in mortar.

This study explores the potential of utilizing stone waste fines as fine aggregate or filler to replace cement in mortars. The critical review presented in this paper discusses the properties of the stone waste fines, mixing procedures, and properties of mortar with limestone, marble, granite, and basalt waste fines for the first time, using a linear regression model. Some findings were: (1) For mortar with stone waste fines as a partial replacement of fine aggregate, it was not possible to establish a trend for compressive strength. The tensile bond and adhesive strength of mortar with marble waste fines can improve for up to 100 % and 60 % substitution. The drying shrinkage may be insignificant, up to 30 %, in substitution of granite waste fines. Mortar with basalt and limestone waste fines shows no mass loss under freeze-thaw effects; (2) For mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine cement, if the paste cement method is used, marble or granite waste fines produce a positive compressive strength at substitution levels up to 20 % and 15 % and the capillarity is lower. Mortar with marble waste fines can reduce shrinkage up to 20 % substitution.

1. Introduction

Industrial and economic development has intensified activities in the construction sector, demanding an increase in the production of building materials such as mortar. Mortar is the second most extensively and generally used construction material worldwide [1]. While traditional mortar exhibits excellent properties, its limitations are becoming increasingly apparent with the advancement of construction technology and the growing demand for environmental protection [2,3]. There is a pressing need to find sustainable solutions and enhance resource utilization [4].

A typical mortar mix consists of three primary components: a binder (usually cement), fine aggregate (river or sea sand or manufactured sand), and water. The binder serves as the adhesive element, while water facilitates proper mixing. Fine aggregate is crucial

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in providing the necessary mechanical strength and durability to the overall mortar mix. Hence, in addition to cement, good aggregate quality is essential in mortar performance [5–7]. However, manufacturing of these products generates environmental repercussions.

On the one hand, cement manufacturing contributes up to 5 % of global CO₂ emissions [8–11]. In recent years, great effort has been made to reduce cement consumption using supplementary cementitious materials (SCM): pozzolans and fillers. Nonetheless, SCM may have limitations due to their availability [12]. On the other hand, the extraction of sand creates a natural imbalance by causing changes in channel hydraulics, contaminating water sources, polluting the environment and destroying local ecology. Also, the continuous extraction of natural sand from riverbeds and sea or coastal is one of the reasons for the disparity between sea sand and coastal sand that creates consequences for coast and flooding in many areas of the world [1,13–15].

Parallel to this, around the globe, the production processes of certain industries—such as quarries, mineral-asphalt mixes, and dimension stone—generate fine waste, commonly referred to as stone waste fines. This finely graded material possesses the necessary characteristics to effectively serve as a replacement for fine aggregate or cement in the construction sector [16]. The unsafe disposal of this waste is one of the significant problems for the environment as well as human health since the leaching of their components may be deposited in soils, surface and groundwater, affecting pastures, livestock farms and crops [1]. A potential solution to these parallel challenges is to recycle the accumulated and continuously generated stone waste, using it as fine aggregate or filler to partially replace cement in mortar.

Two reviews have explored the utilization of different stone waste fines in the preparation of cement composites, either as a replacement for fine aggregate or cement [17,18]. However, they primarily focused on composites, with limited attention to mortar-specific properties. Moreover, crucial aspects of mortar, such as adhesive strength, tensile bond strength or splitting tensile strength, remain underexplored in the literature. The latter does not provide insight into the behaviour of mortars containing fine stone waste when used as rendering mortar. Conversely, the reviews that refer to stone waste in mortar only mention its use as a sand replacement [1,19]. The influence of stone waste fines on the properties of mortars, such as adhesive strength or tensile bond strength, is reviewed in limestone waste fines by Chouhan et al. [1], but the results of the different studies are not correlated. Moreover, special mortars are included in the review, which can distort the results. The influence on properties of mortars with different types of stone waste fines, limestone, marble, and granite, was evaluated by Gehlot and Shrivastava [19]. Furthermore, new properties were reviewed. However, the results of the different studies are not subjected to a critical analysis. The conclusions do not define any optimal replacement level depending on the properties and applications. None of the reviews describe the freeze-thaw resistance in the mortars with stone waste fines despite its importance for its application in cold environments. A critical analysis of stone waste fines properties or the mixing procedures that can influence the properties of the mortars was also not mentioned by other authors.

Fig. 1. Methodology adopted for this review study.

Given these gaps, from the authors' point of view, a new review is necessary to analyse the evaluation of stone waste fines as fine aggregate and as cement partial replacement in cement-based mortars.

The present study attempts to critically review the literature associated with using stone waste fines from limestone, marble, granite, and basalt as replacements for fine aggregate or cement in cement-based mortar. It analyses their impact on fresh state, mechanical, and durability properties.

As literature sources, journal articles indexed in WEB of Science or Scopus have been preferred, but to give a broader view, other scientific sources have also been used. Only articles on stone waste fines in mortar after 2005 and with particle sizes smaller than or equal to 2 mm have been reviewed. Moreover, articles related to stone waste fines in specific cement-based mortars, such as adhesive, self-compacting, hydrophobic or air-cured, were excluded. The keywords used were: *limestone/marble/granite/basalt dust/power/sludge/slurry/fine aggregate mortar/cement mortar*.

The research methodology used in this study is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Out of 50 articles reviewed, over 60 % focused on stone waste fines from marble and granite, 24 % on limestone, and only 10 % on basalt. Among these studies, 4 % compared using limestone and basalt fines in mortars. Additionally, 34 % of the articles explored stone waste fines as a replacement for fine aggregate, while 52 % examined their use as cement replacement in cement-based mortars. The remaining 14 % of studies compared the performance of stone fines as both fine aggregate and cement replacement in mortars.

The paper is divided into several different sections, discussing: (i) the geological nature, origin, and properties of the stone waste fines - section 2; (ii) mixing procedures, methods and properties of fresh and hardened mortar and durability in the presence of stone waste fines depending on their use as partial replacement of fine aggregate or cement - section 3, (iii) pozzolanic activity of stone waste fines - section 4 and (iv) identification of the research gaps - section 5. Summaries of the key finding - section 6 and applications and limitations-section 7 are also included.

1.1. Research significance

This study delves into the use of stone waste as fine aggregate or cement replacement in cement-based mortars. The novelty of this study mainly lies in the compressive analysis of the properties of the stone waste fines, mixing procedures, and the behaviour of mortar with different types of stone waste fines using a simple linear regression model, as well as properties that have not been explored so far. The findings will allow for obtaining global and structured knowledge on cement-based mortars with different stone waste fines and according to the type of replacement selected, such as fine aggregate or cement. Moreover, specific data on optimal replacement ratios are defined according to their properties and potential applications. This is relevant for future research on new fine stone waste and its potential practical applications.

2. Stone waste fines

2.1. Geological nature

Limestone is the most common sedimentary rock made of calcium carbonate. It is usually made of cement, clastic carbonate components or directly precipitated carbonates containing rock-forming carbonate minerals: calcite, aragonite, and dolomite. Contemporary limestone sediments consist of calcite and aragonite CaCO_3 , while in older formations, metastable aragonite has been converted into a permanent form of calcium carbonate - calcite - in earlier formations [20]. Calcium oxide CaO dominates the chemical composition of limestone. Marble is a **metamorphic rock** that forms when limestone is subjected to the heat and pressure of metamorphism. It is almost monomineral and made of calcite, and, in the case of dolomite, it is made of dolomite with a few mixtures, e.g. diopside or mica [21]. Calcium oxides (CaO) and magnesium oxides (MgO) dominate the chemical composition of marble [18]. Granite is a plutonic igneous rock in which alkaline feldspars (orthoclase, microcline, perthite, albite), quartz, and plagioclase dominate the mineral composition [22]. The chemical composition of granite is mainly silica (SiO_2) and aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3). Basalt is a mafic extrusive rock and the most widespread of all igneous rocks. It is volcanic with an aphanitic, fine-crystalline structure, sometimes only with visible pracrystals, and most often with a massive, dense texture. Basalt composition is managed by minerals from the group of sodium-calcium feldspars known as plagioclases, which are accompanied by pyroxenes and amphiboles. The oxides of silicon (SiO_2), aluminium (Al_2O_3), and iron (Fe_2O_3) determine the chemical composition [18].

2.2. Origin

Stone waste fines primarily originate in quarries, mineral-asphalt mixture producers, and dimension stone facilities. In quarries, these fines are generated during the production of crushed stone aggregates. Significant amounts of stone waste fines are produced during extraction, mechanical treatment of rocks, and subsequent sorting operations.

These stone waste fines are also generated in the asphalt plant mix during the capture process of asphalt mixing plants' exhaust gases. Secondary collection equipment is commonly used to capture these very fine-sized materials. Similar waste fines are produced in the dimension stone sector, where stones are treated and subsequently utilized for various dimension applications [18].

The dimension stone industry utilizes a technological process that includes extracting rock blocks, cutting them to the desired size, and smoothing and polishing them.

The stone waste fines generated from these sources and processes can exist in either a dry state or, more commonly, in a moist state or as sludge. This waste is not industrially processed but is collected and either deposited at the quarry or plant site or transported to a

landfill. Regarding the stability of the composition of stone waste fines from various sources—including quarries, mineral-asphalt mixture producers, and dimension stone facilities—the fines from the dimension stone industry may differ depending on the source rock.

It is known that stone fines waste from the cutting, smoothing and polishing processes of the dimension stone industry may contain mixtures such as lime, grit or particles derived from the progressive wear of the elements used in these processes [23]. In all other sources, the fines will depend mainly on the homogeneity of the source rock.

2.3. Chemical composition and physical properties

Most of the reported studies evaluated the chemical and mineralogical composition of stone waste fines to be used as fine aggregate or cement in mortar formulations. On the other hand, properties related to particle size distribution, density and finesses have also been reported in most studies. However, the texture and shape of stone waste fine particles have only been evaluated in some studies, as in Chouhan et al. [24], Dobiszewska and Barnes [25], and Sharma and Vyas [26].

Table 1 summarizes the oxide composition of stone waste fines, including limestone, marble, granite, and basalt. Notably, for limestone and marble waste fines, which consist primarily of calcite (CaCO_3), the literature provides data for calcium oxide (CaO) content, while carbon dioxide (CO_2) content is not specified. Carbon dioxide completes the chemical composition of these fines to 100 % [18]. In contrast, granite and basalt waste fines predominantly contain mass fractions of silica (SiO_2), alumina (Al_2O_3), and iron oxide (Fe_2O_3), consistent with typical igneous rock, accounting for approximately 70 % of their composition.

The size distribution of stone waste fines was evaluated by sieving methods, as in Balasubramanian et al. [14], or laser diffraction, as in Zhang et al. [27].

Table 2 shows the density, fineness, water absorption and specific surface area values of stone waste fines from the reviewed studies.

Density was assessed in most of the studies as relative density/specific gravity [24,32], density/absolute density/specific density/specific mass [12,34] or loose bulk density/bulk density/unit mass [31]. The latter density was less studied in the characterization of waste fines. The results showed that the relative density of the limestone and marble waste fines (carbonated waste fines) can be comparable to and even higher than those of granite waste fines. Basalt waste fines have the highest relative density values. The minerals and porosity of the stone waste fines influence this value. The bulk density depends on the size distribution and shape of the particles [55]. This may explain the variability of bulk density values and why this property of some stone waste fines is higher despite the lower relative or absolute density values, as in the case of some marble and granite waste fines [24,54].

Regarding finesses, some studies adopted slightly different evaluation approaches, such as BET specific surface area [43,46], Blaine specific surface area/Blaine finesses [12,43], laser diffraction specific surface area [46,44] or fineness modulus in Chouhan et al. [24]. The results showed that Blaine specific surface area for the same type of stone waste fines could be in a wide range of values, such as 220–1125 m^2/kg in limestone and 380–1500 m^2/kg in marble waste fines, respectively. This is because the specific area depends on the particle size, and stone waste fines with different particle sizes were evaluated in the studies. The surface area values obtained using the Blaine and BET methods for stone waste fines differ significantly. Specifically, the Blaine method yields a range of 219.9–1500 m^2/kg , while the BET method provides a narrower range of 1300–5700 m^2/kg and higher values. The BET method is more precise for fine particles [56], although the Blaine method is more common (higher available data in the studies, Table 2). The few available data concerning the laser diffraction method are highlighted.

The results showed that water absorption values are scarce and vary by different orders of magnitude, probably related to the test method used. In Gupta and Vyas [51], Kabeer and Vyas [49], and Sharma and Vyas [26], the water absorption was determined in terms of plastic limit. On the other hand, Chouhan et al. [24] do not mention the evaluation method.

In general, the studies do not indicate or describe the standard or method followed for the evaluation of properties of stone waste fines except for a few studies, as in Benjeddou et al. [34] and Lezzerini et al. [57] for the evaluation of size distribution.

Table 1
Chemical composition (%) of limestone, marble, granite, and basalt fines used in previous studies for mortar production.

Oxide composition	Stone fines			
	Limestone (%)	Marble (%)	Granite (%)	Basalt (%)
SiO_2	1.55–23.5	0.36–14.08	59.58–74.39	38.16–56.33
CaO	37.85–56.09	40.73–55.00	0.41–3.80	6.42–15.16
Al_2O_3	0.71–3.10	0.14–2.69	13.01–15.66	7.53–15.05
Fe_2O_3	0.26–1.94	0.04–1.94	0.82–9.77	8.87–17.73
MgO	0.00–1.31	0.48–15.21	0.29–1.87	2.99–10.33
Na_2O	0.016–0.54	0.00–0.91	2.35–5.92	1.72–4.11
K_2O	0.088–0.28	0.03–0.63	3.01–5.02	0.83–1.39
SO_3	0.024–0.88	0.06–0.08	0.00–0.33	0.02–1.10

Sources [24,26–42].

Table 2
Properties of some types of stone waste fines.

Reference	Type of stone waste fines	Specific gravity/relative density	Density/absolute density/specific density/specific mass	Water absorption	Loose bulk density/bulk density/unit mass	Fineness modulus	Blaine specific surface area/Blaine fineness	Laser diffraction specific surface area	BET specific surface area
[43]	Limestone						220–770 m ² /kg		1300–5700 m ² /g
[44]		2.64						1.03 × 10 ⁶ m ² /m ³	
[45]		2.7					380–1125 m ² /kg		
[46]			2.63–2.64 g/cm ³					0.89–0.53 m ² /g	1460–2970 m ² /g
[24]		2.7		8.80 %	956 kg/m ³	1.29			
[47]							860 m ² /kg		
[48]	Marble	2.55					1500 m ² /kg		
[31]		2.5			986 kg/m ³		1140 m ² /kg		
[32]		2.6					329 m ² /kg		
[49])		2.7		18 %	1380 kg/m ³				
[34]			2.7 g/cm ³		610–1120 kg/m ³		386–928 m ² /kg		
[50]			2.63 g/cm ³		1710 kg/l				
[51]	Granite	2.46		15.29 %	1368 kg/m ³	0.9			
[52]		2.62							
[53]							230 m ² /kg		
[54]			2.55 g/cm ³		1070 kg/m ³				
[12]			2.65 g/cm ³				219.9 m ² /kg		
[26]		2.44		13.41 %		1.02			
[29]	Basalt	2.90 g/cm ²							
[25]		2.99					350 m ² /kg		

3. Mixing procedures, methods and properties of mortar mixes

3.1. Mixing procedures

In the literature, various approaches have been explored regarding stone waste fines as a replacement of fine aggregate in mortar: (1) by volume and water/cement (w/c) ratio is not constant, as in Kabeer and Vyas [58], Gupta and Vyas [51] and Chouhan et al. [24]; (2) by mass and w/c is constant, as in Balasubramanian et al. [14]; (3) by mass and w/c is not constant such as Mármol et al. [35], and (4) replacement by the wet packing method [44,59].

In general, when replacing cement in a mortar using stone waste fines, mass substitution is employed. The binder/cement (b/c) ratio can either remain constant, as demonstrated by Khatib et al. [30] or vary, as observed in the work of Benjeddou et al. [34]. However, Li et al. [52,60] concluded that incorporating marble or granite waste fines as a percentage of cement paste is significantly more effective than using stone waste fines for cement. The authors call this method the paste replacement method. Table 3 highlights the types and amounts of replacement of sand or cement with stone waste fines in the preparation of cement-based mortar of the studies reviewed. Some studies used superplasticizer in the compositions of the mortar mixes.

Generally, the preparation and casting of mortar mixes containing stone waste fines are similar to those of normal mortar mixes and are done according to various standard specifications. However, when the waste fines are in the form of sludge, some researchers carry out a previous preparation of the sludge that consists of (1) previous drying, (2) hammering/hand milling/crushing, and (3) passing through a sieve to achieve uniformity for testing of the stone waste sludge, as in Mármol et al. [35], Kabeer and Vyas [58], Xi et al. [69], Amin et al. [33], Benjeddou et al. [34], and Ramadji et al. [12]. Other researchers only describe the drying and sieving procedures of the sludge samples [52,53,59,60,72,73].

3.2. Methods

All tests conducted in the reviewed literature have been summarized in Appendixes A, B, C, and D for fresh, mechanical properties, durability, microstructure examination, and other properties. The studies evaluated workability, consistency, and water-to-cement (w/c) ratio at approximately 70 %. Notably, workability was predominantly assessed in the cement paste, especially when waste fines were used as a substitute for cement, as demonstrated by Abdelaziz et al. [28]. The primary focus for investigating the hardened-state properties of mortar was mechanical strength, which was featured in 94 % of the studies. Flexural strength ranked second, with 32 % of the studies addressing this property. Shrinkage was the next most discussed subject (30 % of the studies). Other properties were evaluated in less than 30 % of the studies.

Table 3
Types of fine aggregate or cement substitution with stone waste fines in cement mortar.

Reference	Type stone waste fines	Method	w/c	b/c	Level of substitution (%)
[27]	Limestone	Aggregate partial replacement	cte		0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25,30 wt
[44]		Aggregate partial replacement ^a	no cte		0, 4, 8, 12 vol.
[28])	Limestone/basalt	Aggregate partial replacement	no cte		0, 4, 8, 12, 16 wt
[29]			cte		0, 20, 30 wt
[24]	Limestone		no cte		0, 20, 40, 60 vol.
[61]			no cte		0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 90, 100 vol.
[48]	Marble		no cte		0, 10 wt
		Cement partial replacement	no cte		0, 10 wt
[42]		Aggregate partial replacement	no cte		25, 50, 75, 100 wt
		Cement partial replacement	no cte		15 % wt.
[62]		Aggregate partial replacement	no cte		0, 25, 50, 75, 100 vol.
[58]			no cte		0, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 vol.
[49]			no cte		0, 10, 20, 30, 40 vol.
[33]			cte		0, 10 wt
		Cement partial replacement	cte		0, 5 wt
[50]		Aggregate partial replacement	no cte		0, 10, 15, 20 vol.
[15]	Granite		cte		0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 100 wt
[37]			cte		0, 10 wt
		Cement partial replacement	cte		0, 5 wt
[51]		Aggregate partial replacement	no cte		0, 30, 40 vol.
[54]			cte		0, 5, 10, 20 vol.
		Cement partial replacement	cte		0, 5, 10, 15, 20 vol.
[59]		Aggregate partial replacement ^a	no cte		0, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100 vol.
			no cte		0, 10, 15, 20, 25 vol.
[63]		Aggregate partial replacement	cte		0, 25, 50, 75, 100 wt
		Cement partial replacement	cte		0, 25, 50 wt
[26]		Aggregate partial replacement	no cte		0, 30 vol.
[38]			no cte		0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 vol.
[64]	Basalt		cte		0, 20, 30, 40, 50 wt
		Cement partial replacement		cte	0, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30 wt
[25]		Aggregate partial replacement	cte		0, 5, 10, 15, 20 wt
[65]	Limestone	Cement partial replacement		cte	0, 17, 23, 27 wt
[43]				cte	0, 15, 25, 35 wt
[66]				cte	0, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12, 14, 18,22, 26, 30 wt
[45]	Limestone		cte		0, 5, 10, 15 wt
[46]			no cte		0, 30, 60 vol.
[67]				cte	0, 10, 20, 40 wt
[30]				cte	0, 5, 10, 15, 20 wt
[47]				cte	0, 10, 20, 30, 40 wt
[31]	Marble			cte	0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 50 wt
[32]			no cte		0, 10, 20, 30, 40, 50 wt
[68]				cte	0, 5, 10, 15, 20 wt
[69]				cte	0, 10, 20, 30 wt
[70]				cte	0, 5, 10, 15, 20 wt
[34]			cte		0, 5, 15, 25 wt
[57]				cte	0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25 wt
[35]	Granite		no cte		0, 5, 10, 20 wt
[36]				cte	0, 5, 10 wt
[71]				cte	0, 10, 20, 30, 40 wt
[53]			cte		0, 10, 20, 25, 30, 35 wt
[12]				cte	0, 10, 15, 20 wt
[39]	Basalt		cte		0, 10, 20, 30 wt
[40]				cte	0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 10 wt
[41]				cte	0, 10, 20, 30, 40 wt
[72]	Marble	Paste partial replacement	cte		0, 10, 15, 20 vol.
[60]			cte		0, 5, 10, 15, 20 vol.
		Cement partial replacement	no cte		0, 5, 10, 15, 20 vol.
[73]	Granite	Paste partial replacement	cte		0, 5, 10, 15 vol.
[52]			cte		0, 5, 10, 15 vol.
		Cement partial replacement	no cte		0, 5, 10, 15 vol.

Abbreviations: cte - constant; no cte - not constant; vol. - by volume; wt. - by mass.

^a Wet packing method [44].

It is highlighted that the adhesive strength of mortar on substrates, according to EN 1015-12 [74], and the tensile bond strength between brick and mortar, according to ASTM C 952 [75], were studied at different levels when stone waste fines were used to replace fine aggregate. However, tensile bond strength was only evaluated in mortar with stone waste fines as a partial replacement for cement.

Durability was discussed in 60 % of the studies. Total water absorption, porosity, and capillarity water absorption/sorptivity were discussed in 48 % of the studies. Only one study investigated the capillary water absorption of mortar containing stone waste fines as a partial replacement of fine aggregate. Durability properties concerning environmental exposure, such as sulphate resistance or freezing and thawing cycles, were present in 14 % and 2 % of the studies, respectively.

On the other hand, microstructural studies were carried out in 40 % of the studies.

Properties were generally evaluated using the normal procedures adopted for conventional mortar mixes.

The reviewed articles have not addressed the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) or Life Cycle Cost (LCC) analysis of mortar with waste stone fines.

3.3. Properties

A simple linear regression model was used to establish the relationship between the effect of different proportions of stone waste fines on the properties of mortar. The boundary conditions and scope of applicability are as follows: analysis with the available data by type of waste; if R^2 is > 0.5 , the data are considered to fit the model; if R^2 is < 0.5 , the data are considered not to fit the model, but the identification of mortar families (or group of families) that to fit the model is carried out.

This finding will allow identifying properties of mortars with stone waste fines, such as fine aggregate or cement, that depend only on one variable, the replacement ratios, which may depend on other variables.

3.4. Fresh properties of cement mortar with stone waste fines

The workability or consistency of fresh cement mortar mix containing stone waste fines was studied extensively; as mentioned in point 1, the consistency of mortar was determined in the cement paste in many studies, mainly with waste fines as a partial replacement of cement.

Figs. 2 and 3 show the relative consistency and/or w/c ratio in mortar with varying stone waste fines content as partial replacement of fine aggregate or cement (only studies that do not use an additive or use the same amount of additive as the control/reference additive mortar are presented). From these figures, it can be concluded that mortars with fine aggregate replacement with stone fines behave differently from those with cement replacement.

3.4.1. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine aggregate

There are not enough results to establish effective correlations that explain the consistency or w/c ratio trends in the mortar with

Fig. 2. Workability of mortar at different types and levels of stone waste fines: (a) relative consistency [14,25,27,54]; (b) w/c [24,26,38,51,49,50,58,61,62].

Fig. 3. Relative consistency of mortar at different types and levels of stone waste fines [35,39,54,68,66,70].

granite fines as a partial replacement of fine aggregate, even though mortar families can establish trends (1°: $R^2 = 0.6$, one mortar family;-; 2°: $R^2 = 0.8$, three mortar families;-; 3°: $R^2 = 0.6$, one mortar family-). Trends can be detected in mortar with limestone or marble and basalt waste fines. A decrease in the consistency or a rise in the w/c ratio as the level of limestone or marble waste fines increases is perceived (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 shows a lower or similar workability value of fresh mortar or a higher required w/c ratio (for the same consistency) compared to the conventional mortar mix due to the incorporation of granite or basalt waste fines.

The reasons for those properties of the mortar mix containing granite or basalt waste fines are: (1) the increase in fineness increased the surface area that requires more water; (2) a greater water absorption potential due to its microstructure and its main chemical components; (3) the angular and rough texture of granite and basalt powder [25,54,51]. For example, Dobiszewska and Barnes [25] found that the flow of the mortar decreases considerably when the basalt waste fines content increases. The addition of basalt waste fines caused a reduction in the initial flow of the mix from 7.12 to 6.34 in. (181–161 mm) for 10 % basalt waste fines incorporation and to 5.67 in. (144 mm) for 20 %. Four hours after mixing the ingredients, vibrating the mortars with 10 %, 15 % and 20 % basalt waste fines addition did not cause the mortars to flow due to their dry consistency. Replacing part of the sand with basalt waste fines increases the specific surface area of the fine aggregate since the fines' specific surface area is much larger than that of the sand, contributing to a significant increase in the water needed to wet the surface of the grains. The consequence is a change in consistency in the direction of less fluidity and reduced workability.

Regarding mortars with limestone/marble as partial replacement of fine aggregate, the main reason behind the decrease in consistency is the fineness. According to Zhang et al. [27], the consistency of the mortar is reduced mainly due to the fineness of the cement ($SSB = 4000\text{--}5200\text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$) and the marble powder ($SSB = 2731\text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$), which is important and increases the water demand.

On the other hand, though a positive trend in terms of consistency is perceived in mortar with limestone/marble waste fines, there is a reduction of the water requirement due to the incorporation of the fines for 10–30 % and 20–75 % replacement ratios respectively (Fig. 2b). The decrease in the w/c ratio of mortar mixes is generally due to the thixotropic property of the marble waste fines [24,49,58,61,62]. Moreover, Chouhan et al. [24] reported that the fall in water demand may be attributed to a filler effect created by the limestone waste fines. The voids between sand particles, which were previously occupied by water, are now replaced by limestone waste fines. This resulted in higher water availability for the lubrication of particles and cement hydration.

3.4.2. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of cement

Fig. 3 shows that the consistency trends can be established in the mortar with granite waste fines ($R^2 = 0.5$) and for one mortar family with marble (1°: $R^2 = 0.9$, one mortar family). The mortar with granite waste fines shows a slight increase in consistency as the level of granite waste fines is higher. However, the mortar with marble waste fines decreases in consistency as the level of waste rises. Regarding mortars with limestone/basalt as a partial replacement of cement, there is not enough data on consistency to establish a

compelling correlation that can be explained. More results would be needed. According to the authors' knowledge, no more data is available on the consistency and replacement ratio of cement with limestone/basalt waste fines.

Generally, it can be ascertained that mortar mixes with granite and basalt fines as partial cement replacement can maintain or improve the consistency of the reference mortar mix (Fig. 3). One reason may be that waste fines have a comparable specific surface to cement, so the increase in waste fines content does not change the normal consistency [40]. In the case of granite, it has a low porosity, which explains this low water requirement [12].

Nascimento et al. [54] reported a slight increase in the consistency index of fresh mortar formulations with the addition of 15 % and 20 % wastes replacing cement; consequently, there was a probable reduction in cohesion since a binder raw material was replaced with an inert one. For the other mixes, there was no change in the consistency index compared to the reference.

Fig. 3 also shows two types of workability behaviour of mortar containing limestone/marble as partial cement replacement. The consistency in mortar with limestone/marble can be higher for substitution levels up to 18 and 20 %. The factor responsible for this increase may be the difference in specific gravities between cement and stone fines. This means that the same weight of limestone/marble replacing cement takes more volume than cement; this increases the total paste volume in mortar mixes, resulting in higher workability for mortar [66,70].

On the other hand, a lower consistency of mortar with cement replaced with limestone/marble is also observed in Fig. 3. According to Israr et al. [68], the flow of cement sand mortar decreases due to a decrease in the pores space between the relative molecules of the marble waste fines, cement and sand. Hence, the particles of the specimen will be tightly packed. However, Michel et al. [43] reported that this effect could mainly be attributed to a worse arrangement of the fine particles and the presence or absence of fine clay particles in the fillers.

3.5. Hardened properties of cement mortar with stone waste fines

Mortar with stone waste fines is evaluated for different physical and mechanical properties. The mechanical properties include compressive and flexural strengths, splitting tensile strength, tensile bond, and adhesive strengths, which are determined by destructive testing, and pulse velocity and dynamic Young's modulus, which are determined by non-destructive testing. However, the available information on the mechanical properties of mortar mixes with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine aggregate or cement is different.

3.5.1. Bulk density/dry density/density/dry unit weight

The density-related properties are studied in many research works related to stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine aggregate [24,25,54,49,50,58,61,62] or cement [54,46,57,68,69,70]. Note that all authors have used a similar method to evaluate the bulk density except for Dobiszewska and Barnes [25], who used the mercury intrusion technique, and Qiao et al. [64], who evaluated the mass. In some cases, it is also unclear whether the density evaluated is the bulk density or the apparent density [42,69]. Moreover, no reviewed studies evaluated the bulk density in a mortar with basalt waste fines as a partial replacement of cement and only one in a mortar with granite waste fines. Figs. 4 and 5 show some results of relative bulk density/dry density/density/unit weight of mortar

Fig. 4. Relative bulk density/dry density/density/unit weight of mortar at different types and levels of stone waste fines [24,25,49,50,61,62].

Fig. 5. Relative dry density/dry bulk density/dry unit weight of mortar at different types and levels of stone waste fines [54,46,57,69,70].

containing stone waste fines at different replacement ratio levels at 28 days. Mortar mixes with stone waste fines show different behaviour when the fines are used to replace fine aggregate or cement.

3.5.1.1. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine aggregate. It is not possible to establish an effective correlation that can explain the bulk density/dry density/density/unit weight trends in mortar with stone waste fines as a replacement of fine aggregate. However, negative trends for mortar families with limestone/marble waste fines can be established. Two negative trends can be detected in two mortar families with limestone waste fines (1°: $R^2 = 0.5$, two mortar families) and one mortar family with limestone waste fines (2°: $R^2 = 0.8$, one mortar family). Regarding marble waste fines, a negative trend is detected in four families (1°: $R^2 = 0.7$, four mortar families) (Fig. 4). This suggests that densities decrease as limestone/marble waste incorporation increases as fine aggregate.

In Fig. 4, the bulk density/dry density/density/unit weight of mortar is slightly higher or the same up to replacement ratios of 40 % with limestone, marble or basalt fines. The bulk density/dry bulk density/dry unit weight of mortars with limestone or marble waste fines incorporation ratios of more than 60 % is lower or the same.

Kabeer and Vyas [49] analysed the bulk and apparent densities and compared their behaviour. The authors found that the peak in the bulk density at a substitution ratio of 20–30 % was because the corresponding mortar mixes had the least water. This might be further aided by achieving a dense packing due to the modified grading of the cement, sand and marble waste fines. When the substitution ratio reached 40 %, despite the lower water content in this mortar mix than in the reference mortar mix, the bulk density reduced to 1.96 g/cc from 2.05 g/cc of mortar mix with a 30 % replacement. This can be because of excessive fines, which may have created voids. It is also seen that the apparent density (impermeable pore space) rose significantly when marble waste fines were used in the mortar mixes. This was because marble waste fines can accelerate the hydration reaction, resulting in a denser microstructure. Because the volume of these hydrated products is always less than the dry constituents and free water, voids are created, which reduces the bulk density. The greater value of apparent density, lower water content, and filler action of the marble waste fines was dominant until 20 % substitution, after which there were sufficient voids to lower the bulk density of the hardened mortars.

3.5.1.2. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of cement. Fig. 5 shows that the bulk density/dry density/density/unit weight in mortar with different stone waste fines contents as replacement of cement shows a decrease in the bulk density of mortar as the level of limestone ($R^2 = 0.7$) or marble waste fines increases ($R^2 = 0.6$).

This behaviour may be related to different reasons. For example, Yamanel et al. [70] observed that dry unit weight values decreased for the specimens with waste marble waste fines as a partial mass replacement of cement; a higher replacement caused a higher reduction in unit weight. According to the authors, this is explained and attributed to differences between the specific gravities of cement and marble waste fines. A higher replacement ratio of higher specific gravity materials with lower specific gravity materials results in a lower unit weight of the final product.

3.5.2. Compressive and flexural strengths

The compressive strength of cement mortar is a fundamental property that has been thoroughly studied in almost all research

related to stone waste fines. However, from the literature reviewed, only Chouhan et al. [24,61], Qiao et al. [64], Dobiszewska and Barnes [25] and Gehlot and Shrivastava [38] evaluated the flexural strength of mortar mixes with stone waste fines as replacement of fine aggregate. More researchers [36,40,41,54,53,69–71] evaluated the flexural strength of mortar mixes with stone waste fines as cement replacement. Figs. 6–9 represent the results from 224 mortar mixes made with different types of stone waste fines in terms of relative strength at 28 days. These figures show that mortars with stone waste fines as fine aggregate replacement show different behaviour from mortars with stone waste fines as cement replacement.

3.5.2.1. *Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine aggregate.* The available results do not allow for establishing effective correlations that explain the compressive strength trend in mortar with stone fines as a partial replacement of fine aggregate (Fig. 6a). The scatter of the results plotted in Fig. 6a may be the outcome of the combined effect of the variables involved with the stone waste fines, such as the variability in chemical composition and physical properties in the same type of stone (Tables 1 and 2). However, trends can be established for mortar families. Two different trends can be detected in mortar with marble waste fines for three mortar families. The positive trend corresponds to two mortar families, one with up to 40 % substitution and the other with up to 100 % of fine aggregate (1°: $R^2 = 0.6$, two mortar families). The negative trend corresponds to one cement-rich mortar family (2°: $R^2 = 0.8$, one mortar family). Two different trends are also observed in two mortar families with basalt waste fines: a positive trend (1°: $R^2 = 0.9$, one mortar family) and a negative trend (2°: $R^2 = 0.9$, one mortar family). The positive trend corresponds to a smaller particle size. Regarding limestone, one type of trend is observed in a mortar family, which is positive (1°: $R^2 = 0.9$, one mortar family) and in granite, one type of positive trend is also observed in a mortar family (1°: $R^2 = 0.9$, one mortar family).

Fig. 6a shows that, in general, all mortar mixes with waste fines and a 10 % replacement ratio maintain or show higher strength values than the reference mortar and some even at higher replacement levels (70 %, 100 % in lean mortar, and 50 % for limestone, marble and granite waste fines respectively) and lower or higher w/c ratios. Mortar mixes with higher replacement levels and higher strengths may be due to a filler effect and other reasons. One is the ability of some minerals to accelerate the hydration reaction, as in the case of marble or limestone or the pozzolanic activity in basalt or granite.

Kabeer et al. [49] reported that, in mortar with marble as a replacement of fine aggregate, the best performance is obtained at lower w/c ratios. Still, an in-depth analysis shows that some mortar mixes have higher compressive strength despite having greater water content. This can be due to the ability of dolomite minerals to accelerate the hydration reaction involving alite, as stated by Szybilski and Nocun-Wczelik [76]. Carbonate-based aggregates also form calcium carboaluminates by suppressing the formation of calcium aluminate hydrate [77]. A similar outcome occurred when marble quarrying waste replaced river sand [62]. However, Dobiszewska and Barnes [25] concluded that this improvement is mainly attributable to the filler effect of the basalt waste fines—i.e. improved particle packing. The large pores in the mortar are filled with basalt waste fines, which leads to better compaction and densification of the structure of the hydrated cement paste and, consequentially, to improved mechanical properties of mortar. Moreover, the

Fig. 6. Relative compressive strength of mortar at different types and levels of stone waste fines: (a) no wet packing method [14,24–28,31,33,37,38, 54,51,49,48,50,58,61,62,64]; (b) wet packing method [44,59].

Fig. 7. Relative flexural strength of mortar at different types and levels of stone waste fines [24,25,61,64].

Fig. 8. Relative compressive strength of mortar at different types and levels of stone waste fines: (a) no paste replacement method [12,32,34,39–41, 54,43,45,53,57,68,64,66,69–71]; (b) paste replacement method [52,60].

improvement of later-age strength may also be due to a pozzolanic behaviour of the basalt waste fines. For their part, Zhang et al. [27] attributed the improvement in compressive strength with the content of limestone waste fines to two reasons: the filler effect and the effect of the ceramic core, which made the hydration products of cement tend to envelop the surface of limestone particles with C-S-H and $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ particles, which led to the strength of interface zone being enhanced. Limestone waste fines can reduce the concentration

Fig. 9. Relative flexural strength of mortar at different types and levels of stone waste fines [36,40,41,54,64,69–71].

of the ionic liquid phase and accelerate the hydration of C_3S , which is conducive to improving the strength after hardening.

Bakhom et al. [37] reported that the higher compressive strength value of mortar with nano-granite waste could be due to the pozzolanic reaction that occurs between nano-granite particles and calcium hydroxide, forming more C-S-H, which is considered the main component responsible for strength in cement-based composites.

On the other hand, the reduction in compressive strength due to using stone waste fines as fine aggregate replacement may be due to the reduction in workability. As described in section 3.1 above, the decreased workability can be attributed to the increased surface area and specific density of the stone waste fines. This decreased workability creates a demand for cement paste volume, resulting in poor compactness, which, in turn, reduces compressive strength [14,27].

It is highlighted that Kwan and McKinley [44] and Chen et al. [59] found that replacing fine aggregate with limestone or granite waste fines up to 12 % and 25 %, respectively, according to the wet packing method, improved compressive strength. According to the authors, this is due to its effect of filling the voids between the fine aggregate particles, thus increasing the packing density. However, a negative trend is observed in a mortar family with granite waste fines with substitution levels of up to 100 % (1°: $R^2 = 0.5$, one mortar family) and with marble with substitution levels of up to 12 % (1°: $R^2 = 0.9$, one mortar family). Moreover, positive trends are only detected in mortar families. Two positive trends are detected in two families of mortar with granite (2°: $R^2 = 0.5$, one family mortar; 3°: $R^2 = 0.7$, one mortar family), and a positive trend is detected with four families (2°: $R^2 = 0.8$, four mortar families) (Fig. 6b).

Regarding flexural strength, a similar performance was observed for compressive strength, as shown in Fig. 7. However, no positive trend has been perceived for some mortar families with limestone or granite waste fines as described for the compressive strength. Only a negative trend is perceived with limestone waste (1°: $R^2 = 0.6$, two mortar families). On the other hand, two different trends are observed in two mortar families with basalt waste fines: a positive trend (1°: $R^2 = 0.8$, one mortar family-) and a negative trend (2°: $R^2 = 0.8$, one mortar family). According to Dobiszewska and Barnes [25], the tendency of flexural strength is very similar to that of compressive strength in mortar with basalt stone fines. Still, the flexural strength increase is slightly less pronounced.

3.5.2.2. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of cement. Fig. 8a shows that only two mortar mixes with waste fines and a 10 % replacement show higher strength values than the reference mortar mix. Moreover, two trends can be detected. One shows a decrease in compressive strength as the level of stone waste fines replacement increases (limestone: $R^2 = 0.7$; marble: $R^2 = 0.5$; granite $R^2 = 0.6$; and basalt $R^2 = 0.5$) (Fig. 8a), and the other indicates a rise in compressive strength as the amount of stone waste fines increases (marble: $R^2 = 0.7$; granite $R^2 = 1$) (Fig. 8b).

These two divergent trends can be explained by the mix design method used. Li et al. [52,60] carried out comparative studies of the cement and paste replacement method for marble and granite waste fines and reported that adding marble and granite waste fines as paste replacement without changing the w/c ratio would always produce a positive change in compressive strength for at least 15 % and 20 % replacement with granite and marble waste fines, respectively. Conversely, adding marble and granite waste fines as cement

replacement without changing the water volume would only produce a slightly positive change in cube strength up to a marble waste fines volume of 5 %. It could produce an adverse change in cube strength (negative change means a decrease) if the marble and granite waste fines volume is increased to 10 % or higher. According to the authors, adding marble or granite waste fines at paste replacement would densify and improve the microstructure of the hardened mortar, whereas adding marble or granite waste fines as cement replacement could cause deterioration of the microstructure. There can be different reasons behind this deterioration of the microstructure [71]: (1) the addition of granite sludge higher than the optimum amount may increase the specific surface area of the aggregate mix that requires an excess amount of cement to bind it [78–80]; (2) as the amount of cement decreases with increasing granite sludge, an excess amount of water is required for workability to increase, resulting in a dilution of the cementitious materials that bind the aggregate mix and in a poorly compacted mix of porous microstructure [78,79,81]; (3) the reduction in strength due to granite waste fines incorporation can be because the binding activity of the granite waste sludge is less reactive than other cementitious materials such as cement [82,83].

Regarding flexural strength, a similar performance was observed for compressive strength. A decrease in flexural strength as the level of stone waste fines replacement by cement increases (marble: $R^2 = 0.9$; granite: $R^2 = 0.6$ and basalt: $R^2 = 0.5$), as shown in Fig. 9. The reasons for this behaviour are the same as those explained for compressive strength. However, in contrast to compressive strength, the substitution of stone waste fines has a negligible effect on flexural strength [41,53,71]. According to Dobiszewska et al. [41], this behaviour is probably related to the large irregularity and roughness of the surface of basalt grains, which have the ability to mechanical wedge in the cement matrix. During the progress of hydration, the amount of C-S-H phase increases, tightly filling the space between irregular grains. This allows for transferring the stress effectively through the basalt-cement paste interface and exploiting the relatively high strength of basalt. After a longer period of hydration, the pores in the ITZ are filled up by the C-S-H phase, and consequently, the probability of finding a critical defect decreases. The macroscopic manifestation of this effect is a much smaller decrease in flexural strength than that caused by the reduction of cement.

Molnar and Manea [42] reported that mortar with a percentage of marble waste fines as a partial replacement of sand had the highest flexural strength value over time of all types of plastering mortar.

3.5.3. Splitting tensile strength

Only two studies are available from the reviewed bibliography on evaluating the splitting tensile strength of mortar mixes containing stone waste fines irrespective of the type of replacement [14,46].

Balasubramanian et al. [14] observed that using granite waste fines as sand replacement has a positive effect on tensile strength compared to cement mortar, and there is a correlation between compressive and splitting tensile strength (Fig. 10).

Maximum tensile strength is achieved for 15 % granite waste fines mortars. However, Costa et al. [46] reported that due to the incorporation of two types of limestone waste fines as cement replacement, the tensile strength diminished between 12 % and 35 % for the mortars with 30 %vol of limestone waste fines, and at 60 %vol, the strength dropped by about 60 % compared to the reference mortar with and without dispersing admixture. Interestingly, the results of tensile strength were clustered in two groups when plotted

Fig. 10. (a) Splitting tensile strength of mortar at different levels of granite waste fines; (b) compressive strength vs. splitting tensile strength of mortar at different levels of granite waste fines (GD) as replacement of fine aggregate (data from Balasubramanian et al. [14]).

as a function of the porosity of the mortars. The results of group REF +30 %vol were at much higher values than those of mortars with 60 %vol of limestone waste fines, indicating that the matrix of the mortars at the highest replacement ratio employed was substantially different from that of the others (Fig. 11).

The causes for the reduction observed in splitting tensile strength reported by Costa et al. [46] were similar to those used to explain the decrease in compressive strength due to the incorporation of stone waste fines. The substitution of cement for almost inert limestone waste fines reduced the mechanical properties of the mortars due to a dilution effect (lower volume of hydrated binding phases); the higher the replacement ratio used, the more significant the reduction was.

3.5.4. Ultrasonic pulse velocity (UPV) and dynamic Young's modulus of elasticity (E_{dy})

The UPV test evaluates the effect on denseness and compactness of mortar mixes. From the literature reviewed, five reports are available on the evaluation of UPV and E_{dy} in parallel [24,51,61,62,64]. The relative results at 28 days obtained in these studies are presented in Fig. 12. In addition, two other studies were identified that analysed both properties independently [49,58]. However, only three studies have been identified on the UPV evaluation of mortar mixes containing stone waste fines as cement partial replacement [57,63,64].

3.5.4.1. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine aggregate. Fig. 12a shows that these are not good UPV results on mortar with stone fines to establish a sound correlation that can be explained in mortar with marble, granite and basalt waste fines. According to the authors' knowledge, no more results are available. However, two mortar families and limestone waste fines can establish a negative trend. (1°: $R^2 = 0.9$, two mortar families) These mortar families correspond to a cement-rich mortar and a mortar with limestone waste fines substitutions of up to 100 %. Fig. 12a reveals that compared to control mixes, mortar mixes with stone waste fines show a higher UPV of up to 40 % replacement, except for the stone waste fines from basalt. The denser CSH may be responsible for providing a better transport medium of the ultrasonic waves than sand. On the other hand, a further increase in the stone waste fines replacement ratio resulted in the non-uniformity of the mix, making it more porous and leading to poor compaction and reduced pulse velocity [24,51,62].

Regarding dynamic E_{dy} , a similar behaviour was observed for UPV. Two negative trends can be detected in two different mortar families with limestone waste fines (1°: $R^2 = 0.6$, one mortar family; 2° $R^2 = 0.8$, one mortar family), as shown in Fig. 12b. Gupta and Vyas [51] observed that the E_{dy} of a 1:4 mortar mix with granite waste fines was higher than that of a control mortar. However, the value of E_{dy} for a 1:6 mortar mix was comparable to that of the control mortar. The authors concluded that the decrement in the w/c ratio is responsible for slightly incrementing the dynamic modulus of elasticity.

Fig. 11. Splitting tensile strength of the mortars with limestone waste fines as cement (cured for 14 days) as a function of their porosity (data from Costa et al. [46]).

Fig. 12. (a) Relative UPV of mortar at different types and levels of stone waste fines; (b) relative E_{dy} of mortar at different types and levels of stone waste fines [24,51,62,64].

Fig. 13. (a) Compressive strength vs UPV of mortar containing marble and basalt waste fines (data from Qiao et al. [64]; data from Lezzerini et al. [57]); (b) UPV of mortar at different levels of granite waste fines (data from Agrawal et al. [63]).

3.5.4.2. *Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of cement.* Lezzerini et al. [57] found an excellent correlation between the uniaxial compressive strength and the UPV of mortar containing marble waste fines as partial cement replacement, following a linear relationship. Fig. 13a shows that the UPV linearly decreases as the specimens' compressive strength decreases in the cement ratio with marble waste fines. However, the mortar with basalt waste fines does not show any correlation in Qiao et al. [64]. On the other hand, Agrawal et al. [63] reported poor UPV values in rich and lean mortar mixes with granite waste fines as cement due to increased voids and lower compaction (Fig. 13b).

3.5.5. Tensile bond strength

The tensile bond strength of mortar mixes containing stone waste fines as fine aggregate replacement [24,26,51,49,58] was studied more frequently than mortar mixes containing stone waste as cement replacement [46]. Using stone waste fines as aggregate or cement seems to present a similar behaviour.

3.5.5.1. *Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine aggregate.* Fig. 14 presents mortar's relative tensile bond strength with varying stone fine content as the partial replacement of fine aggregate. It is perceived that there are not enough results to establish effective correlations that could explain the trend of tensile bond strength vs. stone fines. The tensile bond strength and the replacement of fine aggregate with stone waste fines cannot be statistically related. There may be other parameters that create noise and do not allow a trend to be obtained. This figure shows that incorporating limestone, marble and granite waste fines as fine aggregate can increase the tensile bond strength for up to 60 %, 100 % and 40 % replacement ratios, respectively.

The increase in tensile bond strength may be due to (1) modification of the rheological parameters - the yield stress value reduces, which allows greater penetration of the mortar into the brick, improving the physical interlocking [58]; (2) the lower w/c ratio of mortar mix that resulted in the formation of a stronger bond between brick and mortar [24,51].

Kabeer and Vyas [49] concluded that the tensile bond strength of a mortar mix with 30 % marble waste fines had a slightly higher performance than an equivalent conventional mortar mix. At 40 % substitution, the performance fell by nearly 50 %. According to the authors, the mortar portion of the mix became denser with the increase in the incorporation of marble waste fines. The higher water content in the mixes might be the reason for excess voids. The reduced surface area of contact at the interface may have led to a reduced performance of the mortar/brick adhesion capacity. The author also concluded that the enhancement of tensile bond strength is significant due to the incorporation of marble waste fines in lean mortar mixes [58]. A similar behaviour was observed when the stone waste fines were granite. A mortar with a 30 % replacement ratio of natural sand by volume showed maximum bond strength. The mix with a 40 % replacement ratio of natural sand in mortar by volume had lower bond strength than the 30 % granite waste fines' mortar, and, nevertheless, it is higher than that of control mortar. Hence, mortar with 30 % granite waste fines is best suited for masonry works [51].

Fig. 14. Relative tensile bond strength of mortar at different types and levels of stone waste fines [24,26,51,49,58,61].

Fig. 15. Tensile bond strength of mortar with two types of limestone waste fines (data from Costa et al. [46]).

Fig. 16. Relative adhesive strength of mortar at different types and levels of stone waste fines [24,26,51,58,61].

3.5.5.2. *Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of cement.* Costa et al. [46] reported that the bond strength was not reduced by replacing the binder with limestone waste fines at a ratio of 30 %, even without dispersing admixture (Fig. 15). There was an 18 % and 21 % increase in the bond strength for mortar mixes with two types of limestone waste fines with different particle size distributions compared to the reference mortar. At a replacement ratio of 60 %, a considerable reduction (approximately 35 %) in the bond strength was observed. The dispersing admixture increased the bond strength of all the studied mortars, with an average increase of 29 %.

3.5.6. *Adhesive strength*

Adhesive strength is a fundamental property, as it determines the solid union between the pieces or parts joined together. In addition, in the case of rendering, detachment of the mortar can leave the façade unprotected. Despite the importance of this property from the reviewed bibliography, only studies are available on evaluating the adhesive strength of mortar with stone waste fines as fine aggregate replacement. These studies found that incorporating stone waste fines as fine aggregate can increase the adhesive strength of the resulting mortar [24,42,46,51,58,61].

Fig. 16 shows some results of the adhesive strength performance of mortar containing stone waste fines relative adhesion at different replacement levels. As for compressive and tensile bond strengths, it is observed that the available results do not allow for establishing effective correlations that could explain the trend of adhesive strength in mortar with stone waste fines. This is in agreement with individual studies. These studies indicate that the variation of adhesive strength in mortars is similar to that of compressive strength and tensile bond strength [58]. However, a negative trend has been detected for one marble mortar family (1°: $R^2 = 0.6$, one mortar family). This mortar family corresponds to a cement-rich mortar with marble waste fines.

The figure also shows that the incorporation of limestone or marble waste fines in mortar as fine aggregate can increase the adhesive strength for up to 60 % replacement and, in the case of granite waste fines, up to 40 %. The factor responsible for this increase may be the higher water absorption capacity of stone waste relative to conventional fine aggregate, which results in maximum penetration of mixing water into the pores, thus forming more hydrated products.

Chouhan et al. [61] observed an increase in adhesive strength resulting from a 50 % replacement ratio of river sand with limestone waste fines; at a 60 % replacement ratio, the strength decreased, but it was equal to that of the control mix. However, further addition gave the adhesive strength value less than control. According to the authors, the high-water absorption of limestone waste fines compared to river sand is the primary reason for such behaviour, which resulted in the penetration of mixing water into the pores and played a significant role in the hydration reaction with the strong interface.

For mortar mix proportions of 1:3, 1:4, 1:5 and 1:6 (cement: fine aggregate) and varying substitution ratios of marble powder, the adhesive strength seems to peak at 20 % substitution. Further, an increase in marble waste fines content in mortar mixes reduces the adhesive strength, although, at a 40 % replacement ratio, the strength is still higher than that of the control mix [58]. The same authors concluded that the performance advantage can be credited to the ability of the hydration products to penetrate the bricks. With

Fig. 17. Relative total absorption and porosity at different types and levels of stone waste fines [24,51,49,58,61,62].

marble's capacity to accelerate the hydration process, the strength gain of the hydration products and the mechanical bond between the mortar and brick has improved. Molnar and Manea [42] also recorded a 160 % increase in adhesive strength to the support layer when calcite marble was used instead of 25 % of river sand.

Gupta and Vyas [51] reported that granite-based mortar shows 21 % and 23 % higher adhesive strength than a control mix for 30 % and 40 % replacement ratios, respectively.

3.6. Durability properties of cement mortar with stone waste fines

Several durability factors are evaluated for mortar containing stone waste fines. These include total water absorption, porosity, capillary water absorption, shrinkage, frost resistance, and resistance to sulphate attack, among others. However, compared to the available information on the mechanical performance of mortar containing stone waste fines, there is less information on the durability behaviour of this type of mortar.

3.6.1. Total water absorption and porosity

Total water absorption is an important parameter related to the extent of mortar porosity and its durability performance. From the literature review, studies are available in parallel on evaluating water absorption and permeable voids in mixes containing stone fines as fine aggregate partial replacement [24,51,49,58,61,62] and as cement partial replacement [13,57,69–71]. Figs. 17 and 18 compare some results at 28 days of the water absorption and permeable voids of different stone waste fines as replacement of fine aggregate or cement. These figures show that mortar with fine aggregate replacement with stone waste fines has a similar behaviour to that of mortar with stone waste fines as cement replacement.

3.6.1.1. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine aggregate. The total water absorption and porosity trends cannot be established in a mortar with granite waste fines as the partial replacement of cement. More data are needed. According to the authors' knowledge, no studies are available on total water absorption and porosity in mortar with granite waste fines as a partial replacement of fine aggregate. However, a positive trend of total water absorption and porosity can be observed in mortars with limestone waste fines (total water absorption: $R^2 = 0.9$; porosity: $R^2 = 0.5$) and marble waste fines (total water absorption: $R^2 = 0.8$; porosity: $R^2 = 0.6$) (Fig. 17).

In general, Fig. 17 shows that the water absorption (%) of a mortar mix increases with increasing incorporation of stone waste fines in the mortar. This may be due to increased permeable pore space or porosity, which results in more available space for water absorption. The permeable pore size varies from 0.1 to 10 mm [84,85].

According to Chouhan et al. [24], the improvement in water absorption is explained by a higher water holding capacity and specific

Fig. 18. Relative total absorption and porosity of mortar at different types and levels of stone waste fines [12,57,69–71].

surface area of limestone waste fines compared to river sand. Due to this phenomenon generated more voids in mortar mix with dry limestone waste fines, as seen in Fig. 17. Similar to water absorption, maximum voids were generated at a 60 % replacement ratio. At 20 % substitution of river sand, voids were about 4–15 %, much less than the maximum substitution of river sand with both limestone waste fines.

Kabeer and Vyas [58] found that, at 20 % substitution, the water absorption is equal to or marginally higher than the corresponding control mixes for all series. Primarily, this is because of the greater water absorption capacity of marble waste fines than river sand or the excessively cohesive nature of the mortar mix. Consequently, this has increased the porous volume of this mix. However, Gupta and Vyas [51] found that water absorption reduces for granite waste fines at lower replacement ratios of up to 40 %, beyond which it starts increasing. This behaviour is probably due to the filling of pores (filler effect) by the fine granite waste fines particles up to 20 % replacement ratio. Cement-based adhesive mortar prepared with marble waste fines as a replacement of natural sand shows a marginal change in the water absorption capacity [86]. In contrast, granite waste fines inclusion reduces the water absorption value by 6.6 % and 6.1 % for 30 % and 40 % replacement ratios, respectively. This decrement in value due to granite inclusion is explained by the fewer pores at the interfacial zone, causing a denser mortar mix [84].

3.6.1.2. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of cement. Fig. 18 shows an increase in total water absorption and porosity as the partial replacement of marble (total water absorption: $R^2 = 0.8$; porosity: $R^2 = 0.8$) or granite waste fines increases (total water absorption: $R^2 = 0.8$; porosity: $R^2 = 0.7$).

An effective correlation can be established with the available results. According to Yamanel et al. [70], using marble powder instead of cement as a partial replacement caused an increase in the amount of water absorbed, as well as the porosity of the mortar. This can be attributed to the inert nature of the waste marble, which does not have hydration properties with water. Replacing waste marble does not contribute to hydration. Thus, a greater content of waste marble waste fines means less cement and less hydration products in the mortar mix. In addition, increasing the marble content increases the water-cement ratio. This increases the porosity and, hence, the water absorption capacity.

3.6.2. Capillary water absorption/sorptivity

Capillarity water absorption concerns the penetration of liquids such as water within permeable bodies to definite heights, allowing the detrimental materials to be transferred and freeze, causing a deterioration in the building materials [71]. Relative to water absorption by immersion, less information on mortar's capillary water absorption/sorptivity behaviour with any stone waste fines is available. Only Chen et al. [59] reported the sorptivity of mortar containing stone waste fines as partial fine aggregate replacement. More information has been reported on mortar with stone waste fines as a partial replacement of cement [12,57,69,71–73].

Fig. 19. Sorptivity coefficient of mortar at different levels of granite waste fines and w/c (data from Chen et al. [59]).

Fig. 20. Relative capillary water absorption/sorptivity at different types and levels of stone waste fines [12,57,65,69,71].

3.6.2.1. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine aggregate. Chen et al. [59] reported that the sorptivity, adding granite waste fines to replace up to 15 % sand by wet packing method lowered the sorptivity coefficient (i.e. increased the watertightness) with a constant w/c ratio (Fig. 19). According to the authors, the effect of granite waste fines on the watertightness may be explained by the corresponding changes in packing density and permeable porosity.

3.6.2.2. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of cement. Fig. 20 shows that the capillary water absorption of the mortar increases with the increase in stone waste fines content as a replacement for cement (limestone: $R^2 = 0.6$; marble: $R^2 = 0.5$; granite: $R^2 = 0.5$). Furthermore, the increase of the capillary absorption is smaller for granite waste fines incorporation.

This capillary absorption increase may be due to the larger capillary pores and porosity due to the higher fineness of stone waste fines than cement or the high substitution ratio of cement with stone waste fines, which reduces the cement content and increases the w/c ratio.

Mashaly et al. [71] reported that the sorptivity (absorption in mm) of mixes increased with increasing granite waste fines incorporation ratios, and it reached a maximum height of 6.9 mm and 7.4 mm in the initial and secondary absorption, respectively, for mortar mixes at 40 % substitution. However, the mortar mixes, including up to 20 % granite waste fines as cement replacement ratio, exhibited a water penetration resistance better than the other mixes with substitution ratios beyond 20 %, consistent with the water absorption results. The reason behind the penetration reduction is that, at a substitution ratio of 20 %, the granite waste fines act as pore filling between cement particles and between cement and aggregates, as well as filling the capillary pores, reducing the connectivity and, in turn, decreasing the water permeability. Beyond the 20 % cement replacement ratio, because the granite waste fines have higher fineness than cement, the specific surface area of the mixes rises, which is attributed to the high specific surface area of the granite waste fines. This increases water demands needed for lubrication and leads to a potential reduction in cementitious materials required for the binding activity between material mix, resulting in a more porous microstructure and larger capillary pores.

Ramadji et al. [12] measured the capillary water absorption of different mortar mixes containing various granite waste fines. Their results revealed that the presence of granite waste fines in the mortars has a negative effect on the sorptivity. According to the authors, when replacing CEM I with granite waste fines, the pore size increases. As porosity also increases, this leads to an increase in the absorption coefficient and the sorptivity. Xi et al. [69], using marble waste fines as cement partial replacement, concluded that the reference mortar showed the lowest values of capillary water absorption.

On the other hand, it is highlighted that capillary water absorption decreases with the use of marble or granite waste fines as a replacement for cement. Li et al. [72,73] reported that using marble and granite waste fines to replace up to 20 % and 15 % of cement, respectively, according to the paste partial replacement method, lowered the sorptivity coefficient (i.e. increased the watertightness) for a constant w/c. Further, at a lower w/c ratio, reducing water absorption is generally more complex. This is probably because, as the porosity falls due to lowering the w/c ratio, the pore size is also reduced, leading to larger water capillary suction into the pores. Quite possibly, the same mechanism has led to a lower effectiveness of adding marble or granite waste fines as paste replacement in reducing the water absorption at a lower w/c ratio.

3.6.3. Drying shrinkage

Drying shrinkage may lead to cracking in mortars. Drying shrinkage can be defined as the volumetric change owing to mortar drying. This change in the volume of the mortar is related to the volume of water lost. This loss (free and adsorbed water) may lead to tensile stresses, which force mortar to shrink, causing cracks that can adversely affect its durability and serviceability. When shrinkage is restrained, it causes internal tensile stress, resulting in shrinkage cracks. Thus, the drying shrinkage reduction capacity of marble

Fig. 21. Drying shrinkage of mortar at different types and levels of stone waste fines as replacement of fine aggregate: (a) limestone (data from Chouhan et al. [24]); (b) marble (data from Khyaliya et al. [62]); (c) granite (data from Gupta and Vyas [51]); (d) granite (data from Sharma and Vyas [26]).

waste fines is found to be significant and favourable. The drying shrinkage test is one of the important parameters used to observe the ability of mortar to be used for its practical application. This property of mortars is mainly related to the available cement content, water content and relative humidity. The drying shrinkage of mortar mixes containing stone waste fines has been studied extensively [12,25,27,31,40,41,49,45,59,68,66,67,71,73,74]. The drying shrinkage presents a similar behaviour in mortar with stone waste fines as aggregate or cement, although for different reasons and with some exceptions.

Fig. 22. Drying shrinkage at different types and levels of stone waste fines as replacement of cement: (a) limestone (data from Khatib et al. [30]); (b) marble (data from Yamanel et al. [70]); (c) granite (data from Ramadji et al. [12]); (d) basalt (data from Dobiszewska and Beycioğlu [40]).

3.6.3.1. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine aggregate. In general, incorporating stone waste fines as fine aggregate increases the drying shrinkage of the resulting mortars (Fig. 21). The causes of this behaviour may be the lower fineness of stone waste fines than fine aggregate or the higher water loss due to a w/c ratio greater of mortar with stone waste fines.

Chouhan et al. [24] noticed that the drying shrinkage of mortar increases with an increase in the limestone waste fines' proportion in the mixes. The reason behind this negative effect is the improvement in fineness of the mix upon inclusion of limestone waste; however, at 20 % substitution, this effect is insignificant. At this ratio, the w/c ratio was lowest and similar to that of the control mixes, which justifies the comparable drying shrinkage value obtained. Beyond 20 %, the fineness phenomena become a dominating factor, increasing drying shrinkage. Marble waste fines can also follow this path [58]. For all the mixes, the drying shrinkage increased as the marble content rose from 0 % to 100 %. At a substitution ratio of 20 %, the drying shrinkage of some mortar mixes was comparable to that of the control mortar. According to the authors, drying shrinkage occurs as a result of water loss from the mortar mixes.

Marble-incorporated mixes have greater water content when compared to their corresponding control counterparts, which might be why their drying shrinkage is greater. However, mixes with a 20 % substitution of river sand have less water than the corresponding control mixes. This should have made these perform better than the corresponding control mixes. However, since drying shrinkage also depends on the aggregates' surface area, the waste fines' fineness has offset the positive effect due to reduced water content. Gupta and Vyas [51] showed that the shrinkage of mortar increased with the increase of the content of granite waste fines replaced by natural sand. On the other hand, mortar prepared with 30 % granite waste fines was comparable to the control mortar in shrinkage.

Khyaliya et al. [62] reported that drying shrinkage was the same at the end of 28 days of testing for control and 50 % marble mortar mixes. Hence, cracking and exposure of protected surfaces will not be a concern when marble is used up to a replacement level of 50 %.

3.6.3.2. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of cement. Fig. 22 shows that the drying shrinkage of a mortar mix increases with the increase in the incorporation of limestone, granite, and basalt waste fines in the mortar as cement but not for marble waste fines. The factors responsible for this increase may be (1) the pore size of stone waste fines; (2) a higher w/c ratio due to the decrease of cement content; (3) a weaker microstructure due to lower hydration (4) an increase of capillary pores in the mortar with stone waste fines.

Khatib et al. [30] found higher drying shrinkage by increasing the limestone waste fines content. At 28 days, the incorporation of 20 % limestone waste fines achieved the highest value (925 mm/m). According to the authors, the increase in drying shrinkage of the mortar samples might be due to the pore size of limestone waste fines. Besides, the increase of drying shrinkage magnitude of the mortar specimens indicates that mortars had extra water in their pores, which was then evaporated with time. The extra water content in the mortar samples affected the drying shrinkage. Furthermore, the addition of limestone waste fines content to the fixed amount of sand and cement required more water to improve workability. This might increase the shrinkage value.

From their experiments on using limestone filler as a partial replacement for cement in the preparation of mortar, Courard et al. [65] reported a decreasing trend of shrinkage with increasing limestone filler content. According to the authors, this is due to the

Fig. 23. Drying shrinkage rate of mortar at different levels of marble and granite waste fines and w/c (paste replacement method) (data from Li et al. [72,73]).

decrease of the cement content and rise in w/c ratio as the substitution ratio increases (considering that the cement content decreases when cement is substituted with limestone filler). Ramadji et al. [12] also reported higher shrinkage of mortar prepared by replacing various fractions of fine aggregate with granite waste fines than the control mortar. According to the authors, this behaviour could be explained by two hypotheses. The first is that the low hydration in granite waste fines mortars did not allow the microstructure to resist capillary pressure. Secondly, it can be said that there are many capillary pores in mortars containing granite waste fines, which increases the capillary pressure and causes a significant shrinkage.

Dobiszewska and Beycioğlu [40] observed that, after 14 days of curing, the shrinkage strain of all mortars with the addition of basalt waste fines was lower than that of the control mortar. However, with passing time, the shrinkage of all mortars with basalt exceeded that of control mortar. The partial replacement of cement with basalt waste fines led to an increase in the effective w/c ratio from 0.5 for the control mortar to 0.56 for the mortar with a 10 % addition of basalt waste fines. This increased water demand is supposed to cause greater drying shrinkage.

Regarding marble waste fines, Yamanel et al. [70] measured the drying shrinkage property for one year. The authors found that the shrinkage of all mortars with marble waste fines increased with increasing time intervals. The hydration of cement causes this since shrinkage is a function of the hydration of cement. However, partially replacing marble waste fines with cement caused a reduction in shrinkage value in comparison to the control cement mortar. A higher replacement ratio of marble waste fines results in a higher reduction in shrinkage relative to the control cement mortar. This is attributed to reduced cement content due to its partial replacement with marble waste fines. Shrinkage is known to be a function of the hydration of cement, and marble waste fines are known as an inert material.

On the other hand, it should be noted that the drying shrinkage decreases when marble or granite waste fines are used instead of cement paste (Fig. 23).

Li et al. [72,73] reported that adding marble or granite waste fines to replace up to 20 % and 15 % cement, respectively, according to the paste replacement method without changing the w/c ratio, always reduced the shrinkage and the reduction in shrinkage was generally larger at lower w/c ratio. According to the authors, this is because a slower rate of development of shrinkage strain would allow more time for the creep of mortar to take place and a greater portion of the tensile stress induced by shrinkage movement restraints to be relieved by creep (or relaxation) to avoid shrinkage cracking. Irrespective of the w/c ratio, the development rate of shrinkage strain is slower with granite waste fines with up to 10 % replacement ratio than with marble waste fines, as shown in Fig. 23.

3.6.4. Resistance to sulphate attack

In the literature, only two studies on the evaluation of the resistance to sulphate attack on mortar mixes containing stone waste fines as fine aggregate are available [62,63] and five as cement replacement ratio [12,63,65,66,71].

Fig. 24. Relative change in compressive strength of mortar with different levels of marble waste fines as replacement of fine aggregate over the exposure time to (data from Khyaliya et al. [62]): (a) sulphate solution; (b) acidic medium.

3.6.4.1. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement ratio of fine aggregate. Khyaliya et al. [62] examined the resistance of mortar with marble waste fines to sodium sulphate and sulphuric acid solutions. The authors concluded that mortar mixed with 25 % sand and replaced with marble appeared to be the most stable at 7 and 28 days. When exposed to aggressive environments to sodium sulphate or sulphuric acid solutions, the change in compressive strength was less than that of the control mortar. In general, the incorporation of marble has rendered the mixes comparatively inert to any change in compressive strength. This occurs despite the increase in porosity (Fig. 24).

In particular, the 50 % replacement ratio mix performed similarly to the control until 7 days of exposure to an acidic medium, after which the fall in compressive strength was quite large. The unexpected result in compressive strength at 7 days of exposure might be because of a pore-filling effect of products. This increased the already higher compressive strength. This is confirmed by the increase in weight at the same exposure period. After 7 days, the expansive products might have induced internal stresses that affected the compressive strength significantly more than any other mix.

3.6.4.2. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of cement. Courard et al. [65] determined the resistance to sulphate of mortar with limestone waste fines as cement replacement by the changes in the length of prismatic specimens when stored in a standard sulphate solution. The authors observed that the sulphate resistance of the mixes with Portland cement and limestone is influenced by the filler, especially at a substitution ratio of 15 % (Fig. 25a). However, Hang et al. [66] reported a strength loss of mortar with limestone waste fines smaller than the reference mortar after immersion for more than 56 days in a sodium sulphate solution (Fig. 25b).

According to the authors, this is because limestone waste fines have the role of closely packed physical and chemical activation. They can promote the hydration of C3A, accelerate cement hydration, and turn single sulphur-type hydration of calcium sulphoaluminate into stable single-carbon hydrated calcium aluminium [87]. This makes limestone waste fines mortar denser and stronger than pure cement paste.

Mashaly et al. [71] reported that mortar mixes with granite waste fines exhibited weight gains comparable to or slightly greater than the control mortar mix. In contrast, the mortar mix with a 40 % replacement ratio showed an incipient weight loss. Confinement of the formed ettringite to the internal void space may have accounted for no mass loss in the test specimens (Fig. 26a). The visual appearance of the mortar mixes after immersion in a sulphate solution up to 15 days revealed that there were no signs of surface erosion, cracking or destruction compared to the condition before they were exposed. The impact of sulphate attack on the mortar mixes in terms of strength loss against granite waste fines replacement showed a general trend toward the increase in loss percentage in compressive strength with increasing granite waste fines replacement ratios. The minimum compressive strength loss was observed for the mortar mix with a 10 % granite waste fines replacement. Ramadji et al. [12] found that the mass loss of mortars with granite waste fines as cement replacement was lower than that of the control mix (Fig. 26b). When sulphuric acid reacts with the hydration products,

Fig. 25. (a) Relative deformation of mortar at different levels of limestone waste fines as replacement of cement (data from Courard et al. [65]); (b) Compressive strength of mortar at different levels of limestone waste fines over the exposure time to the acid (data from Hang et al. [66]).

Fig. 26. (a) Relative mass loss of mortar at different levels of granite waste fines (data from Mashaly et al. [71]); (b) relative mass loss at different levels of granite waste fines over the exposure time to the acid (data from Ramadji et al. [12]).

the hydrated composites dissolve and hydrogen ions form [88]. Among the hydrated products, portlandite is the most soluble in sulphuric acid [89]. There is little portlandite in the cement matrix due to the dilution of cement by the granite waste fines.

3.6.5. Freeze-thaw resistance

Aral and Cihan [29] reported the freeze-thaw resistance of mortar containing limestone and basalt waste fines as a substitution of fine aggregates by using the standard method. A freeze-thaw test was performed according to ASTM C-666 [89], and 40 cycles were realized. The following conclusions were taken from the results: (1) as the replacement ratio increased, the weight loss and compressive strength decreased but the ultrasonic pulse velocity and flexural strength generally increased; (2) as the number of cycles increased, the weight loss increased for 30 % of limestone incorporation and reference samples but for the other samples the weight loss was stable; (3) as the number of cycles increased, ultrasonic pulse velocity increased but compressive strength and flexural strength decreased (Fig. 27). The fact that waste fines types have no significant effect on compressive strength and flexural strength is due to the similar fineness of the waste fines materials.

4. Pozzolanic activity of stone waste fines

Medina et al. [90] studied the pozzolanic activity of granite waste fines in a pozzolan/ $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ system. They reported that pozzolanic activity was similar to that pozzolanicity reported for other additions (copper and SiMn slag) but lower than found in pozzolans, such as silica fume, traditionally used in cement. Furthermore, Medina et al. [53] determined the pozzolanicity of granite waste fines by measuring the activity index. The strength activity index (SAI) at 28 days in mortars was higher than the 75 % required by standards ASTM C 618 for fly ash or natural pozzolans and 70 % EN 450-1 for fly ash for cement replacement ratios of 20 % y 25 % respectively. Ramos et al. [36] used the Frattini test described in standard EN 196-5 to evaluate the pozzolanicity of granite waste fines. The existence of pozzolanic activity was confirmed. In contrast, Ramadji et al. [12] reported that granite waste fines do not exhibit pozzolanic activity. Both the Frattini test and the modified Chapelle test were used. A study [91] showed that basalt waste fines from crushing plant had potential pozzolan activities. SAI at 7 and 28 days was similar to fly ash according to the requirements of ASTM C618 for fly ash [92].

5. Research gaps

Based on a detailed literature review, several research gaps have been identified for future directions to develop sustainable cement-based mortars using stone waste fines.

Fig. 27. Freeze-thaw resistance at different levels of basalt and limestone waste fines as replacement fine aggregate: (a) mass loss; (b) UPV; (c) compressive strength; (d) flexural strength (data from Aral and Cihan [29]).

Regarding the type of stone waste fines, a detailed and systematic study is needed concentrating on the effect of basalt waste fines incorporation as fine aggregate or cement replacement on the physical, mechanical and durability property performance of mortar since a very limited number of studies are available.

Some results on hardened properties of mortar are available, but most studies discuss mortar compressive strength for up to 28 days

only. Additional studies on other properties are necessary to provide a clear understanding of the effect of stone waste as fine aggregate or cement on mortar mixes. It is necessary to establish trends or clearly identify the reasons for the scatter of results. In general, durability is poorly studied. Important parameters have not been studied or have been studied only to a limited extent. Therefore, a detailed investigation on waste as fine aggregate must be carried out according to the type of mortar, i.e. masonry or rendering mortar, external or internal application.

5.1. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine aggregate

Although properties on consistency or w/c ratio in the fresh state have been studied, to the authors' knowledge, no studies are available on the rheology of mortar with stone waste fines as a replacement for fine aggregate. Such tests can help explain the behaviour of mix produced with stone waste fines. Workability-related properties are essential to establish the criteria for applying this type of mortar on site, especially in rendering mortar.

More studies should evaluate the flexural strength of mortar with fine aggregate replaced with stone waste fines, as it is an important parameter for masonry mortar.

Despite the importance of capillary absorption, especially in rendering mortar, as a durability-related parameter, to the authors' knowledge, only one study on mortar with granite waste fines as a replacement of fine aggregate was identified. Moreover, the authors of that study applied the wet packing method for fine aggregate replacement. Concerning environmental exposure resistance, only two articles have discussed the resistance to sulphate attack and the freeze-thaw resistance.

5.2. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of cement

To the authors' knowledge, the effect of stone waste fines incorporation on splitting strength and adhesive bond strength (ASTM C 952 [75]) has been very poorly studied, and adhesive strength (EN 1015-12 [74]) has yet to be assessed, as these are important parameters for rendering mortar.

Although parameters affecting durability, such as capillary absorption or porosity, have been evaluated in mortars with stone waste fines as cement replacement, to the authors' knowledge, no study has discussed freeze-thaw resistance.

6. Critical analysis

This review discusses the effects of incorporating stone waste fines as a partial replacement for fine aggregate or cement in cement-based mortars, focusing on their fresh, hardened, and durable properties. The key findings are summarized below:

6.1. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine aggregate

Fresh properties - mortars with stone waste fines from igneous rocks generally exhibit lower or similar workability compared to conventional mixes or require a higher water-to-cement (w/c) ratio for equivalent consistency. Contrasting results were found for mortars with limestone or marble waste fines, with some studies reporting an increase and others a decrease in the w/c ratio.

Hardened properties:

- Compressive strength: no consistent trend was found for compressive strength, although mortars with up to 10 % stone waste fines often maintain or exceed the strength of control mortars; limestone waste fines can enhance strength at substitution ratios up to 70 %; marble waste fines can increase strength by up to 2.2 times at 100 % substitution in lean mortar (ratio 1:6); and granite waste fines improve strength up to 50 % substitution (no data available above this level);
- Tensile bond and adhesive strength: it was not possible to establish a trend in the mortar mixes with stone waste fines. However, incorporating limestone, marble, or granite waste fines often enhances these properties: marble waste fines improve tensile bond strength up to 100 % replacement; adhesive strength increases significantly with limestone or marble fines (up to 60 % substitution) and granite fines (up to 40 %);
- Durability - total water absorption increases with limestone and marble waste fines due to higher porosity, though granite waste fines do not significantly increase absorption at up to 40 % substitution; drying shrinkage increases with all types of stone waste fines but may be insignificant for limestone or marble at up to 20 % substitution and granite at up to 30 %; mortars with 25 % marble waste fines exhibit excellent resistance to sodium sulphate and sulphuric acid. Basalt and limestone waste fines show no mass loss under freeze-thaw conditions, with compressive strength loss decreasing after ten cycles.

6.2. Mortar with waste stone fines as partial replacement of cement

Fresh properties - incorporating stone waste fines as a cement substitute can maintain or improve mortar consistency due to their comparable specific surface area to cement and, in the case of granite, low porosity.

Hardened properties:

- Compressive strength: two contrasting trends were identified - a decrease in strength as substitution increases when using the cement replacement method and an increase in strength when fines densify the microstructure using the paste replacement method,

particularly for marble (up to 20 %) and granite (up to 15 %). Adding marble or granite waste fines without altering water volume slightly enhances compressive strength up to a 5 % substitution ratio;

- Durability - capillary water absorption increases with higher substitution ratios of limestone, marble, and granite waste fines. However, paste replacement methods can reduce absorption at substitution levels of 20 % for marble and 15 % for granite. Mixed results were observed for drying shrinkage: marble waste fines can reduce shrinkage at up to 20 % substitution, and granite and basalt waste fines generally lead to higher shrinkage. Regarding resistance to sulphate attack, mortars with granite fines show increased strength loss exposure, with the lowest loss observed at 10 % substitution.

Using stone waste fines as a partial replacement for fine aggregate yields better mortar properties than using them as a replacement for cement. Based on the reviewed articles, a maximum threshold model is established to offer practical design data (Tables 4 and 5).

7. Applications and limitations

Based on the results analysis of this review and requirements (according to the type of application and exposure) of Spain's 2019 Technical Building Code (CTE) approved in 2006 [93], the potential applications and limitations of cement-based mortars with stone waste fines are discussed.

7.1. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine aggregate

Cement-based mortars with stone waste fines as replacement for fine aggregate can be used for both applications: masonry and rendering/plastering mortars. The porosity of mortar mixes with limestone and marble as the replacement of fine aggregate increases; therefore, its use will be limited in high-humidity outdoor environments and capillary water absorption requirements W2 ($0.20 \text{ kg/m}^2 \text{ min}^{0.5}$). This would not be the case in mortars with granite waste fines if the packing method is used, due to the capillary absorption can be lower than that of the reference mortar. Mortars with marble waste fines show a resistance to sulphate attack acceptable; therefore, it can be suitable in weak aggressive chemical exposure environments. These mortars can be used in aerial marine environments because they are cement-based mortars and no expansion by lime nuclei is foreseen.

7.2. Mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine cement

The use of cement-based mortars with stone waste fines as replacement or cement is slightly more limited than as fine aggregate, although it can be used in both applications. The applications as rendering/plastering will be limited to mortars of strength type CS II ($1.5\text{--}5.0 \text{ N/mm}^2$), CS II ($3.5\text{--}7.5 \text{ N/mm}^2$) due to its compressive strength decrease. This would not be the case in mortars with marble or granite waste fines if the paste method is used due to its compressive strength increases. The water absorption requirements of mortar mixes with limestone and marble as replacement of fine aggregate increases; therefore, its use will be limited in high humidity outdoor environments and capillary water absorption requirements W2 ($0.20 \text{ kg/m}^2 \text{ min}^{0.5}$). This would not be the case in mortars with marble or granite waste fines if the cement paste method is used due to decreased capillary absorption. Mortars with limestone or granite waste fines show a lower resistance to sulphate attack; therefore, they cannot be suitable in aggressive chemical exposure environments. However, the frost resistance of mortar with limestone and basalt is high; therefore, it can be used in environments with ice-thaw attack.

Table 4
Maximum threshold model for mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine aggregate.

Properties		Method	Maximum threshold				
			Type of stone waste fines				
			Limestone	Marble	Granite	Basalt	
Fresh properties	Consistency	Aggregate replacement	10 %	–	20 %	20 %	
	w/c		50 %	100 %	50 %	–	
Hardened properties	Bulk density/dry density/density/dry unit weight	Aggregate replacement ^a	60 %	100 %	–	–	
			Compressive strength	80 %	100 %	50 %	15 %
	Flexural strength	Aggregate replacement	15 %	–	60 %	–	
	Splitting tensile strength	Aggregate replacement	60 %	–	40 %	20 %	
	UPV		–	–	25 %	–	
	E_{dy}		60 %	100 %	40 %	10 %	
	Tensile bond strength		60 %	60 %	40 %	10 %	
	Adhesive strength of mortar		60 %	100 %	40 %	–	
	Durability	Absorption and porosity		60 %	80 %	40 %	–
		Capillary water absorption/sorptivity	Aggregate replacement ^a	10 %	10 %	40 %	–
Drying shrinkage		Aggregate replacement	–	–	25 %	–	
Resistance to sulphate attack		Aggregate replacement	20 %	50 %	<30 %	–	
Freeze-thaw resistance		–	25 %	–	–		
			20 %	–	–	30 %	

^a Wet packing method [44].

Table 5
Maximum threshold model for mortar with waste stone fines as partial cement replacement.

Properties	Method	Maximum threshold				
		Type of stone waste fines				
		Limestone	Marble	Granite	Basalt	
Fresh properties	Consistency	Cement replacement	22 %	20 %	20 %	30 %
Hardened properties	Bulk density/dry density/density/dry unit weight		30 %	30 %	5 %	–
	Compressive strength		12 %	50 %	10 %	3 %
Durability	Flexural strength	Paste replacement	–	20 %	15 %	–
	Splitting tensile strength	Cement replacement	–	5 %	10 %	<5 %
	UPV		<30 %	–	–	–
	E_{dy}		–	<5 %	<25 %	<10 %
	Tensile bond strength		–	–	–	–
	Adhesive strength of mortar		30 %	–	–	–
	Absorption and porosity		–	–	–	–
	Capillary water absorption/sorptivity		–	10 %	10 %	–
	Drying shrinkage		<15 %	10 %	10 %	–
	Resistance to sulphate attack		<5 %	20 %	<10 %	<10 %
			<10 %	–	10 %	–

Table 6
Potential practical applications and limitations for mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of fine aggregate.

Type of exposure	Type of application	Masonry mortar					Rendering/plastering mortar			
		Masonry			Flooring		Indoor	Outdoor ^a	Outdoor	
		Partition walls	External walls		Piece by piece	Spreading the bonding material on the floor				
			Masonry	Exposed masonry			Masonry	CS II	CS III	CS III
		M-5	M-5	M-5	M-5	M-2.5	CS II	CS III	CS III	
		M-7.5	M-7.5	M-7.5		CS III	CS IV	CS IV		
						CS IV	W0	W1		
						W0		W2		
General	Indoor	X	X	X	X	X	X	n.a.	n.a.	
	Outdoor	n.a.	X	X	X	X	n.a.	X	n.a.	
Specific	Marine	n.a.	X	X	X	X	n.a.	X	X	
	Other chlorides (non-marine)	n.a.	nn.	nn.	nn.	nn.	n.a.	nn.	nn.	
	Aggressive Chemistry	Weak	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
		Medium	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
		Strong	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
	With frost	Freeze-thaw	n.a.	X	X	X	X	n.a.	X	X
		Fluxing salt	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	nn.	nn.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.

M-X: compressive strength; CSII: 1.5 5 N/mm²; CS III 3.57.5 N/mm²; CS IV ≥ 6 N/mm²; W0: capillary water absorption not specified; W1: capillary water absorption 0,40 kg/m² min^{0,5}; W2: capillary water absorption 0,20 kg/m² min^{0,5}. n.a.: not applied; nn.: unknown.

^a No permeability requirements.

It is highlighted that, although the CTE does not provide requirements on shrinkage mortar values, the application of cement-based mortars with stone waste fines as replacement of fine aggregate or cement waste fines will be limited in dry humidity environments, except for mortars with marble. Appropriate constructive solutions will be necessary to avoid this limitation.

Tables 6 and 7 summarise potential practical applications and limitations based on the reviewed articles and CTE's requirements.

8. Conclusions

The critical review presented in this paper discusses the properties of the stone waste fines, mixing procedures, and properties of mortar with stone waste fines (limestone, marble, granite and basalt) using a linear regression model and practical applications. Based on the results analysed in this review, the main conclusions are as follows:

Table 7
Potential practical applications and limitations for mortar with stone waste fines as partial replacement of cement.

Type of exposure	Type of application		Masonry mortar					Rendering/plastering mortar		
			Masonry			Flooring		Indoor	Outdoor ^a	Outdoor
			Partition walls	External walls		Piece by piece	Spreading the bonding material on the floor			
				Masonry	Exposed masonry					
			M-5				M-2.5	CS II	CS III	CS III
			M-5	M-5	M-5			CS III	CS IV	CS IV
			M-7.5	M-7.5	M-7.5			CS IV	W1	W2
								W0		
General	Indoor		X	X	X	X	X	CS II CS III	n.a.	n.a.
	Outdoor	Medium humidity	n.a.	X	X	X	X	n.a.	CS III	n.a.
		High humidity	n.a.	–	–	–	–	n.a.	n.a.	W1
	Marine	Aerial	n.a.	X	X	X	X	n.a.	X	X
		Other chlorides (non-marine)	n.a.	nn.	nn.	nn.	nn.	nn.	n.a.	nn.
Specific	Aggressive Chemistry	Weak	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
		Medium	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
		Strong	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
	With frost	Freeze-thaw	n.a.	X	X	X	X	n.a.	X	X
		Fluxing salt	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.	nn.	nn.	n.a.	n.a.	n.a.

M-X: compressive strength; CSII: 1.5–5 N/mm²; CS III 3.5–7.5 N/mm²; CS IV ≥ 6 N/mm²; W0: capillary water absorption not specified; W1: capillary water absorption 0,40 kg/m² min^{0,5}; W2: capillary water absorption 0,20 kg/m² min^{0,5}. n.a.: not applied; nn.: unknown.

^a No permeability requirements.

- (1) A linear regression analysis has allowed establishing trends albeit to a limited extent. The data shortage or variability of the chemical composition and physical properties for the same type of waste may be the explanation;
- (2) Threshold values for the different properties and types of waste were identified. Using stone waste fines as partial replacement for fine aggregate yields better mortar properties than using them as replacement for cement. The use of the paste replacement method can reduce this difference. The potential applications of cement-based mortars with stone waste fines as replacement or cement have been defined;
- (3) Existing literature on using stone waste fines as a cement replacement in mortars is limited. Studies on key properties such as adhesion and tensile bond strength, which are critical for mortar performance, are scarce. Additionally, research on the behaviour of mortars with stone waste fines under aggressive environmental conditions remains scarce. For those reasons, the available data limit correlations, boundary conditions, and mathematical models;
- (4) Further investigations are required to optimize the use of stone waste fines in mortars. For practical applications, comparing the LCA and LCC metrics of mortars containing stone waste fines with those of conventional masonry or rendering mortars is essential.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

María Concepción Pacheco-Menor: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Inês Flores-Colen:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Jorge de Brito:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2025.112503>.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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